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This article provides a brief historical overview of the emergence of consulting as a service and entrepreneurial activity. It also analyzes the classification methods for consulting services. The author also attempts to examine this classification by highlighting some controversial issues that hinder the creation of a universal (unified) classification.

Keywords: Classification, consulting services, technology, criteria, competitiveness, universal.

The consulting services market is experiencing significant positive momentum, driven by a variety of factors. The most prominent driver of growth is the ever-increasing complexity of business operations in a context of heightened economic turbulence. Many companies are experiencing difficulties in resolving their operational issues and, therefore, are turning to experts for advice. Experience shows that digital transformation, regulatory compliance, and operational efficiency have recently become the most in-demand areas in this regard. Rapidly evolving technologies and the emergence of new digital solutions are further expanding the capabilities of consulting firms and expanding their range of services. Furthermore, a significant focus on data analysis is enabling consulting organizations to find, process, and provide information that significantly assists in strategic decision-making, ultimately enhancing a company's competitiveness.

The growing global economy is also creating additional opportunities for consulting firms, forcing them to expand their operations into other markets. Small and medium-sized businesses constantly require competent and timely advice, particularly in areas such as marketing, finance, and management. Furthermore, the growing interest (and concern of global businesses and the public) in sustainable development and corporate social responsibility is driving businesses to seek out consultants who can help implement environmentally friendly initiatives and enhance their social impact.

At the beginning of the last century, the history of human development was marked by powerful technological progress, which demonstrated the inadequacy of previous approaches to enterprise organization, structure, and management. Businesses began to experience a severe information hunger, which extended not only to specific encyclopedic knowledge, but also to a greater extent to the skills and abilities that could make a company relevant to new market conditions and able to withstand increasing competition. This prompted the emergence of new specialists called consultants. The first of these were Frederick Taylor, Harrington Emerson, and Arthur D. Little, whose work in the field of scientific organization of labor and production efficiency brought them worldwide fame. It was also around this time that the first consulting company, Booz Allen Hamilton, emerged, founded in 1914 by Edwin Booz as a business research service [1]. Firms like this were very few in number, and the issues they

addressed were highly specific and, as a rule, covered human resource management or sales activities.

As the market and business developed, it became clear that strategic, marketing, and personnel planning were essential for improving business efficiency. This need was reinforced during this period by interest in consulting from the public sector and military. Later, in the years following the end of World War II, demand for consulting services began to grow particularly rapidly. This was driven by post-war construction, the internationalization of industry, trade, and finance, and the increasing role of technological progress in production.

Currently, the global consulting market is actively growing. According to Mordor Intelligence, it will reach \$447.72 billion by 2029. Over the next five years, it will grow at an average annual growth rate of 4.81% [2]. If we consider the next 10 years, the consulting services market size is forecast to grow from \$218.59 billion in 2024 to \$356.06 billion by 2034. Moreover, the average annual growth rate will exceed 5% during the forecast period (2024-2034). Industry revenue in 2025 is expected to be \$227.33 billion [3].

These figures speak for themselves, but despite the highly developed and rapidly expanding global consulting market, a universal and unified classification of this type of service currently lacks. Despite numerous attempts to classify consulting services, the scientific literature is replete with a large number of approaches and classification methods based on various criteria and characteristics.

Among the first to attempt to identify the characteristics of consulting services was W. Stanton. This researcher defined them as belonging to the sphere of business and other professional services [4]. In subsequent years, other scholars went further and identified a distinctive feature in this group of services, which became the main characteristic of consulting – professional, applied in the field of consulting activities. Based on this, D. Thomas created his own classification, in which consulting services are directly interdependent with the services of professional workers and the use of labor [5]. Based on this, this characteristic represents professional advice and recommendations provided by both external and internal specialists.

Research into the classification of consulting services has revealed that a single, so-called universal classification that satisfies a wide range of requirements does not exist. However, some of the most practical classification methods are nevertheless worth

highlighting in this article. Table 1, for example, presents subject-based and methodological classification methods for consulting services.

Table 1

Methods of classification of consulting services

Classification methods:			
Subject-specific		Methodological	
Management consulting	The program is aimed at optimizing the organization's core business processes. This includes: - marketing (improving the effectiveness of methods) target audience research), - HR (for optimal recruitment, further development of their skills, and improvement of corporate culture), - Strategic (adaptation and implementation of new market research methods, risk assessment, and development of organizational development plans).	Expert consulting	Invited experts (consultants) independently solve assigned tasks without the assistance of the team.
Financial consulting	Aimed at creating a reliable, functional financial system. Its types include: - budgeting (optimization of the company's budget, targeted allocation, optimization as needed); - investment (engaging independent experts to understand the appropriateness of investments in other business projects, possible attraction of third-party investments based on expert consultations); - accounting (developing the most optimal and rational accounting system for the company, consulting during the reporting process); - tax (enabling the proper preparation and submission of tax reports, and in certain cases, enabling the most rational approach to taxation from a perspective of reducing the amount of taxes).	Process or project consulting	It is used to conduct joint sessions with the customer's company team to find the best ways to improve business processes and then implement them.
Manufacturing consulting	Aimed at possible cost reduction and improvement of the quality of the company's goods and services.	Educational consulting	Training is provided to company executives and managers, providing them with the latest information on the most relevant methods of doing business.
1	2	3	4

It's worth noting that the consulting market has undergone significant changes over its evolution, resulting in some areas becoming completely different or even disappearing entirely. A prime example of this is services for creating and establishing online sales channels. Currently, they no longer represent a separate consulting area, but are part of a comprehensive suite of strategic services. The same is true for marketing. Strategic marketing issues are included in the services offered by strategic management consulting companies. All other elements of marketing consulting are significantly segmented, and companies typically utilize only specific areas. For example, there are companies in the market whose primary specialization is SMM or branding services, advertising launches or SEM, and SEO optimization.

As noted above, the global consulting and scientific community constantly strives to find a universal

way to summarize the types of consulting services and create a unified and understandable classification (suitable for changing market conditions). However, the number of different approaches continues to grow, with authors continually inventing new types and subtypes. The most well-known and widely used classification is the FEACO classification [6]. According to this reference book, consulting activities encompass 84 types of services, grouped into the following categories:

- general management;
- administration;
- financial management;
- human resources (HR);
- marketing;
- production;
- IT consulting;
- specialized services [6].

A detailed examination of this classification reveals some points (though not entirely logically accurate) that merit attention. The distinction between general management and administration is questionable. According to the classification's authors, the latter concerns the optimization of processes, operations, and activities, while the former is responsible for strategic matters. This distinction is understandable when viewed through the lens of company planning and management, but it seems inappropriate when viewed from a consulting perspective. Therefore, an expert cannot develop a company strategy without taking operational activities into account, and vice versa.

Another important issue is that IT consulting in this classification refers to services for connecting automated business accounting systems and other elements of business automation. This clearly represents a very narrow and simplified approach to this type of consulting. This is not in line with modern realities, as IT consulting encompasses a very diverse field with a wide range of services. These include: creating and establishing online sales channels, digitalizing a company's business processes, working with CRM systems, cybersecurity, cloud technologies, and much more.

Another highly controversial issue is the severe fragmentation of services with little in common. For example, FEACO includes legal services, engineering, and public sector consulting in a single category. However, the criteria are not defined, leading to some uncertainty and difficulty in assigning specific activities to specific consulting groups.

Nevertheless, despite the aforementioned problematic issues raised by the aforementioned classification, its importance and value should be noted, given the fact that it was the first widely recognized attempt to bring order to the rather diverse consulting services market. Many researchers and businesspeople still rely on it, recognizing it as authoritative.

It's important to understand that the consulting industry is particularly vulnerable to change due to rapidly evolving technologies. And in an increasingly competitive environment, consulting companies are constantly shifting their focus from one service to another, exploring new niches. All of this is done to maintain profitability.

Thus, an examination of the classification of consulting services and an attempt to identify new criteria

for creating a universal classification revealed that the modern consulting services market is demonstrating a steady growth trend driven by the increasing complexity of business processes, globalization, and the digital transformation of the economy. At the same time, consulting has emerged as a key element of strategic management, supporting companies in decision-making through expert knowledge, developing human capital, and enhancing competitiveness. All of this is occurring amidst constant structural changes in the market, resulting in the emergence of new service forms, necessitating the development of new types of consulting.

However, it's worth emphasizing that a unified, universal classification of consulting services remains lacking in both scientific and practical terms. Existing approaches (such as the FEACO classification) can only highlight certain aspects without considering dynamics, which prompts further theoretical and methodological research to select and refine criteria for consulting activities. This will ultimately make the market more transparent and improve the quality of services provided.

References

1. Management consulting. / Edited by M. Kubr. In 2 volumes. - M.: Interexpert, 1992. - V. 1. 319 p.
2. Plotnikova V. Technologies, Flexibility, Personnel. Prospects and Trends of Consulting in Russia and the World / <https://sber.pro/publication/tehnologii-gibkost-personal-perspektivi-i-trendi-konsaltinga-v-rossii-i-mire/?ysclid=mfyznznr38318934072> (accessed September 25, 2025)
3. <https://www.fundamentalbusinessinsights.com/ru/industry-report/consulting-services-market-10549>
4. Stanton W.J. Fundamental of Marketing, 1964 // *McMillan Dictionary of Marketing and Advertising*. - Chippenham, Wilshire, 1996. P. 235-240.: <https://www.sovremennoopravo.ru/>
5. Thomas D.R.E. Strategy Is Different in-Service Businesses // *Harvard Business Review*. 1978. № 56. P. 158-165. <https://www.sovremennoopravo.ru/>
6. European Directory of Management Consultants. 1995. London: FEACO-AP Information services, 1995.